

Promoting Scientific Literacy by Teaching in Primary Education the Issue of "Biomass for Biodiesel"

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Abstract

In exploring the integration of biomass education into the primary education curriculum for biodiesel production, the purpose of this study is twofold. Firstly, it aims to highlight the importance of incorporating renewable energy concepts into early education to foster environmental consciousness and sustainability practices from a young age. By teaching students about the potential of using biomass for biodiesel, they can develop an understanding of alternative energy sources and their impact on reducing carbon emissions. Secondly, this study provides practical insights into how educators, as the key players, can effectively implement biomass topics in primary school classrooms. The provision of strategies, resources, and lesson ideas empowers educators, making them feel capable and confident in their role. This ultimately equips students to address the challenges of a changing world. Through this dual purpose, the study not only empowers educators but also contributes significantly to the ongoing discourse on sustainable education practices in primary schools, making them feel part of a larger, impactful movement.

Keywords: *Biomass for Biodiesel, Primary Education, Environmental Awareness, Renewable Energy Education, Scientific Literacy.*

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Introduction

Biomass for biodiesel production has garnered considerable attention in recent years due to its potential to address environmental concerns and reduce reliance on finite fossil fuels (Abdullah et al., 2017; Hamza et al., 2021). This study aims to explore the feasibility and effectiveness of integrating the teaching of biomass for biodiesel production into primary education curricula. Educators in primary schools, curriculum developers, and researchers in environmental education and sustainable energy play a pivotal role in instilling an appreciation for environmentally friendly practices and encouraging critical thinking about energy consumption in young students. Their influence in integrating this topic into the curriculum is crucial, as it can enhance students' understanding of scientific concepts and foster a sense of responsibility towards the environment. Through this research, we aim to provide valuable insights

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into the potential benefits and challenges of teaching biomass for biodiesel in primary schools to promote a more sustainable future for future generations.

Biomass has long been recognized as a promising alternative energy source due to its abundant availability and potential for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Eldiehy et al., 2022). In recent years, a growing interest has been in utilizing biomass to produce biodiesel, a renewable and environmentally friendly fuel used to power vehicles (Hajjari et al., 2022). The use of biomass as a feedstock for biodiesel production has gained traction due to its carbon-neutral nature, as the CO₂ released during combustion is balanced by the CO₂ absorbed during the growth of the biomass feedstock. This sustainable aspect of biomass-derived biodiesel makes it an attractive option for reducing dependence on fossil fuels and mitigating climate change. Research in this field has demonstrated the feasibility and efficiency of biomass conversion processes into biodiesel, highlighting the potential for widespread adoption (Ogunkunle & Ahmed, 2019). The feasibility and efficiency of biomass conversion processes are key factors that instill confidence in the potential of this research. Through continued research and innovation, the development of biomass for biodiesel holds promise for a more sustainable energy future (Scragg, 2009).

An essential aspect of primary education involves introducing students to innovative and sustainable practices early on. Teaching biomass as a source for biodiesel in primary schools holds significant importance in fostering environmental awareness and scientific curiosity among young learners. By incorporating biomass and biodiesel production lessons into the curriculum, students can develop a foundational understanding of alternative energy sources and their role in mitigating environmental challenges. This approach promotes scientific literacy and cultivates a sense of responsibility towards sustainable practices from a young age. As highlighted, providing comprehensive information on research areas and interdisciplinary topics can enrich the educational experience for both students and teachers (Moirano et al., 2020; Kumar, 2016). Through engaging and informative instruction, students can be inspired to become future stewards of the environment, equipped with the knowledge and skills to make informed decisions for a sustainable future.

Understanding Biomass for Biodiesel

Biomass refers to organic materials, such as plants, wood, agricultural residues, and animal waste, that can produce energy through various processes, such as combustion, gasification, or fermentation. In biodiesel production, biomass is essential in providing feedstock for producing renewable fuels (Carpenter et al., 2014). It is seen as a more sustainable alternative to fossil fuels, as it can be replenished within a relatively short period of time. Biomass also helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependency on non-renewable resources (Thornley et al., 2015; Güney & Kantar, 2020). Primary schools can educate students about sustainability and environmental conservation using biomass for biodiesel production. It provides a practical example of how renewable resources can be harnessed to meet energy needs while minimizing environmental negative impacts. Using biomass in primary education can foster a sense of environmental responsibility and encourage students to seek innovative solutions to energy challenges (Scragg, 2009).

Biodiesel production from biomass has gained significance in recent years as an alternative renewable energy source (Wang et al., 2021). Understanding the various types of biomass available for biodiesel production is essential for maximizing

efficiency and sustainability in this process (Molino et al., 2018). Different feedstocks, such as algae, vegetable oils, animal fats, and waste cooking oil, can be utilized for biodiesel production, each with unique properties and challenges. Algae, for example, are highly efficient in oil yield per acre but require significant investment in cultivation and processing infrastructure (Demirbas & Fatih-Demirbas, 2010). On the other hand, waste cooking oil is easily accessible and environmentally friendly but may have limited availability for large-scale production (Singh et al., 2021). By comprehensively understanding the characteristics and potential of different biomass feedstocks, educators can effectively teach students in primary schools about the importance of sustainable energy sources like biodiesel. When teaching about biomass for biodiesel, it is essential to emphasize the need for a diversified approach to feedstock selection to ensure long-term viability and environmental benefits. Highlighting the importance of research and technological advancements in improving biodiesel production processes can inspire future generations to contribute to developing sustainable energy solutions (Nicholls, 2008).

One of the critical advantages of producing biodiesel from biomass is its potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on fossil fuels (Sri Shalini et al., 2021). The process involves several steps, starting with collecting biomass feedstock such as vegetable oils, animal fats, or waste cooking oil. Next, the feedstock undergoes a transesterification reaction with a catalyst, typically sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide, to break down the triglycerides into biodiesel and glycerin (Athar & Zaidi, 2020). The resulting biodiesel is then purified through processes such as washing and drying to remove impurities and excess methanol (Chozhavendhan et al., 2021). Finally, the purified biodiesel can be used as a renewable alternative fuel source for diesel engines. This process highlights the importance of sustainable practices in producing biofuels to mitigate environmental impact (Cheng, 2017).

The environmental benefits of utilizing biomass for biodiesel production cannot be overstated (Abbasi & Abbasi, 2010). Biomass, such as agricultural waste, algae, or even organic municipal waste, offers a renewable and sustainable source of energy that can help reduce our dependence on fossil fuels. Not only does the production of biodiesel from biomass result in lower greenhouse gas emissions than traditional diesel, but it also helps reduce the overall carbon footprint. Using biomass for biodiesel production can also help mitigate waste management issues by repurposing organic materials that would otherwise end up in landfills (Babu et al., 2022). By incorporating biomass into the energy mix, we can move towards a more environmentally friendly and sustainable future for future generations. This shift benefits the environment and promotes a more circular economy that prioritizes resource efficiency and conservation (Speight & Singh, 2014).

The transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources, such as biodiesel derived from algae or microbial oils, presents a promising avenue for mitigating environmental challenges associated with carbon emissions (Bencresciuto et al., 2024). By comparing these alternative fuels to traditional fossil fuels, it becomes evident that biodiesel production from oleaginous microorganisms offers distinct advantages, including higher oxidation resistance and improved technological properties for applications in biodiesel and biolubricants. Furthermore, innovative processes like the proposed extraction of Omega-3 fatty acids from algae-derived biodiesel contribute to the carbon-neutral fuel market and highlight the potential for value-added products in the renewable energy sector (Peters et al., 2019). These advancements underscore the viability of biomass-based fuels as sustainable alternatives to fossil fuels, showcasing

their potential to address the pressing need for cleaner energy solutions in the primary education curriculum on biomass for biodiesel production.

Integrating Biomass for Biodiesel into Primary Education Curriculum

An essential step in integrating biomass for biodiesel into the primary education curriculum is to engage students in hands-on activities that demonstrate the process of converting biomass into fuel (Dahiya, 2014). Students can better understand sustainable energy sources and their environmental impact by incorporating interactive experiments and demonstrations. Additionally, educators should emphasize the importance of renewable energy sources in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and mitigating climate change. Integrating biomass for biodiesel into the curriculum not only provides students with valuable knowledge about alternative energy sources but also instills a sense of environmental responsibility at a young age. Primary schools can significantly shape future generations of environmentally conscious citizens by fostering a solid foundation in sustainability education. Furthermore, incorporating biomimicry principles in the curriculum can enhance students' understanding of how nature can inspire innovative solutions for sustainability challenges (United States. Subcommittee on Energy and Water, 2005).

Developing an engaging and informative curriculum for young learners is imperative to teach biomass for biodiesel in primary schools effectively. The curriculum should incorporate hands-on activities, such as experiments or field trips (Holstermann et al., 2010), to help students better understand the concept of biomass and its conversion into biodiesel. Additionally, the curriculum should include age-appropriate materials and resources, such as videos, interactive games, and worksheets, to cater to various learning styles within the classroom (Oktaweri et al., 2019). Incorporating real-world examples and case studies can help students see the relevance of biomass for biodiesel in their daily lives. By developing a comprehensive curriculum tailored to primary school students' needs, educators can instill a strong foundation of knowledge and awareness about sustainable energy sources early, setting the stage for future environmental stewardship.

In designing teaching methods and strategies for primary school students learning about biomass for biodiesel, educators must consider age-appropriate instructional techniques that cater to diverse learning styles. Combining hands-on activities, visual aids, and interactive discussions can help engage young learners and facilitate a better understanding of complex scientific concepts. Teachers should also incorporate real-world examples and practical experiments to demonstrate the application of biomass technology in a tangible way. Peer collaboration and group projects can encourage teamwork and critical thinking skills, fostering a dynamic learning environment. By employing various teaching methods, educators can create a stimulating and interactive classroom experience that promotes student engagement and comprehension of the subject matter. This approach enhances academic achievement and instills a lifelong interest in sustainable energy practices among primary school students (EduGorilla Prep Experts, 2022).

Educators in the primary school setting require a diverse range of resources and materials to create dynamic and engaging lessons that cater to the needs of their students. These resources can include textbooks, workbooks, manipulatives, multimedia tools, and hands-on materials. In teaching about biomass for biodiesel,

educators may also need access to scientific journals, articles, and research papers to stay informed about the latest developments in the field. Additionally, professional development opportunities such as workshops, conferences, and online courses can help educators enhance their understanding of complex scientific concepts and improve their teaching strategies. By utilizing various resources and materials, educators can cultivate a stimulating learning environment that encourages critical thinking, creativity, and a deeper appreciation for the subject matter. Investing in quality resources and materials can improve student and educator outcomes (Science Teachers Association of Nigeria, 2007).

When considering effective teaching strategies in primary schools focused on biomass for biodiesel education, incorporating hands-on activities for students plays a crucial role in enhancing their learning experience. As highlighted in (Mitra et al., 2015), programs such as one-week summer institutes have successfully engaged educators across various disciplines in bioenergy and bioproducts, introducing them to multidisciplinary approaches and providing curricular materials for a sustainable bioenergy curriculum. Similarly, the summer camp organized at North Dakota State University, as discussed in (Lin et al., 2007), emphasizes interactive projects and exploratory learning experiences for tribal college students, aiming to stimulate critical thinking and introduce them to scientific research methods in science and engineering fields. By implementing hands-on activities like experimental studies and engaging projects, educators can foster a deeper understanding and interest in biomass and biodiesel concepts among primary school students, promoting a holistic approach to STEM education.

As educators strive to enhance their teaching methods in primary education, using practical assessment and evaluation techniques plays a crucial role in monitoring student progress and understanding the effectiveness of instructional strategies. Different types of assessments, such as formative assessments, summative assessments, and performance-based assessments, can provide valuable insights into students' learning outcomes and areas for improvement. It is essential for teachers to regularly assess student understanding to tailor their instruction accordingly and address any misconceptions that may arise. Therefore, incorporating various assessment tools, such as quizzes, projects, and presentations, can help create a comprehensive evaluation of student learning. By utilizing various assessment techniques, teachers can gather diverse data points to inform their teaching practices and support student growth and development (Rosillo-Calle et al., 2015).

Benefits and Challenges of Teaching Biomass for Biodiesel in Primary Schools

Teaching biomass for biodiesel in primary schools offers numerous benefits while presenting distinct challenges. On the one hand, incorporating this topic into the curriculum provides students with a foundation in renewable energy sources, environmental sustainability, and the importance of reducing dependence on fossil fuels. This can empower them with the knowledge and skills to address pressing global climate change and energy security issues. However, the challenges of teaching biomass for biodiesel at the primary education level may include specialized training for teachers, access to appropriate resources and materials, and potential complexities in explaining advanced scientific concepts to young learners. Despite these obstacles, the potential long-term benefits of early exposure to this topic make it a valuable

addition to primary education. Overall, the benefits outweigh the challenges, making it a valuable endeavor for educators (Srivastava et al., 2020).

1. Students Cognitive Development

Teaching primary school students about biomass for biodiesel can significantly impact their cognitive development, as evidenced by various studies on related educational interventions. The Cognitive Acceleration through Science Education (CASE) program, implemented in Ireland, demonstrated that structured science education can enhance cognitive development in students (McCormack et al., 2014). This program, adapted for primary and secondary school transitions, showed significant cognitive gains in students who participated compared to those who did not receive the intervention. This suggests that introducing complex scientific concepts, such as biomass for biodiesel, at an early age could similarly foster cognitive growth. Integrating interdisciplinary STEM content, such as biomass and biofuels, into educational curricula has improved teachers' understanding of fundamental STEM concepts, which can translate into more effective teaching strategies for students (Clase et al., 2014). This approach aligns with findings from a study on biomass education in American agricultural programs, highlighting the importance of incorporating economic, environmental, and pedagogical factors into teaching to prepare students for complex problem-solving (Han & Martin, 2018). By teaching primary students about biomass for biodiesel, educators can cultivate critical thinking and problem-solving skills, essential components of cognitive development. However, it is crucial to consider potential negative associations, such as those found in a study on biomass fuel use in Nepalese households, which linked biomass exposure to lower cognitive abilities in children (Kvestad et al., 2022). While this study focused on environmental exposure to biomass rather than educational content, it underscores the importance of context and the need to carefully consider how biomass topics are introduced in educational settings. In summary, teaching primary school students about biomass for biodiesel can enhance cognitive development by fostering critical thinking and interdisciplinary understanding. However, educators must ensure the content is delivered to maximize educational benefits while minimizing potential negative associations with biomass exposure. As demonstrated by successful programs, integrating these topics into a well-structured curriculum can lead to significant cognitive gains in students (Kong & Wang, 2023).

2. Environmental Awareness and Sustainability Education

Teaching primary school students about biomass for biodiesel can significantly enhance environmental awareness and sustainability education, as evidenced by various research findings. Environmental education (EE) aims to foster attitudinal changes in students, enabling them to evaluate and express concern for sustainable development (SD) (Goel et al., 2022). Integrating EE with climate change education (CCE) and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is crucial for promoting environmental literacy and action among students (Hernández-Barco et al., 2022). Sustainability competencies, such as systems thinking, collaboration, and action-oriented skills, are essential components of primary school education for sustainable development (Vesterinen & Ratinen, 2023). These competencies are developed through dialogue and collaboration, encouraging students to use their imagination to achieve environmental goals in their daily lives. Teaching biomass for biodiesel can incorporate these competencies by engaging students in systems thinking about energy sources and their environmental impacts, fostering collaboration in group projects, and promoting action-oriented learning through hands-on activities. Bio-based experiential

learning, which includes activities like urban farming, has proven effective in raising environmental awareness among children (Arief et al., 2021). This approach educates students about environmental issues, instills social responsibility, and motivates them to consider environmentally friendly business ventures, such as biotechnology, for sustainable urban development. By teaching about biomass for biodiesel, educators can leverage experiential learning to provide practical insights into renewable energy and its role in sustainability. However, challenges remain in effectively implementing and evaluating environmental and sustainability education programs. Research suggests the need for improved evaluation instruments and greater engagement from families and society to enhance the impact of these programs (Agirreazkuenaga, (2022). By addressing these challenges and integrating comprehensive educational strategies, teaching about biomass for biodiesel can play a pivotal role in fostering environmental awareness and sustainability education among primary school students.

3. Practical Skills Development

Teaching primary school students about biomass for biodiesel production can significantly contribute to their practical skills development, particularly in the context of STEM education. Integrating biomass education in schools is crucial for preparing students with the necessary skills to address complex environmental and energy challenges. This approach aligns with the findings from a study on American agricultural education programs, which emphasize the importance of incorporating biomass energy topics to enhance students' STEM skills (Han & Martin, 2018). Workshops and educational programs introducing teachers to interdisciplinary STEM content through biomass and biofuels research have positively impacted teachers' understanding of fundamental STEM concepts. For biomass for biodiesel, the analysis of STEM is presented in Table 1. These programs, which include hands-on activities and guest lectures, help teachers convey complex scientific principles to students, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of biomass and its applications in bioenergy (Clase et al., 2014). The production of biodiesel from biomass involves processes such as transesterification, which can be taught to students to illustrate practical applications of chemistry and engineering principles. Using heterogeneous catalysts derived from biological waste in biodiesel production offers a sustainable and environmentally friendly approach, which can be an engaging topic for students. This teaches them about renewable energy sources and the importance of sustainability and waste management (Abdullah et al., 2017; Hamza et al., 2021).

Table 1. Biomass for Biodiesel: STEM Details

Aspect	Details
Science	Teaching biomass for biodiesel involves understanding biological processes and environmental science.
Technology	Students learn about the technological applications of biomass in energy production.
Engineering	Concepts such as transesterification in biodiesel production illustrate engineering principles.
Mathematics	Mathematical skills are applied to calculate energy outputs and efficiencies in biodiesel production.

Understanding the pathways for converting biomass into bioenergy, including biodiesel, can help students appreciate the broader implications of biofuels in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and addressing the global energy crisis. This knowledge can

inspire students to pursue careers in renewable energy and environmental science, contributing to a more sustainable future (Osman et al., 2022). Overall, teaching primary school students about biomass for biodiesel production can enhance their practical skills in STEM, promote environmental awareness, and encourage sustainable practices, preparing them for future challenges in the energy and environmental sectors.

4. Community Engagement and Outreach

Community engagement and outreach are crucial components in teaching primary school students about biomass for biodiesel, as they foster mutual learning and enhance educational outcomes. Various strategies and findings from different contexts can inform the integration of community engagement in educational settings. Firstly, community engagement initiatives, as seen in primary healthcare settings, emphasize the importance of involving community members in the planning and delivering educational content. This approach ensures that the educational material is relevant and accessible to the students, increasing engagement and learning outcomes (Erku et al., 2023). Similarly, involving community stakeholders, such as local agricultural experts and educators, in teaching biomass energy can help tailor the curriculum to meet the students' and the community's needs and interests (Han & Martin, 2018). Strategic outreach efforts can enhance the success of community engagement in educational projects. The Wisconsin Study Center's experience with community outreach highlights the effectiveness of using broad and targeted interactions to inform and engage community members (Riesch et al., 2012). Applying similar strategies in teaching biomass for biodiesel could involve organizing community workshops and demonstrations that illustrate biomass energy's practical applications and benefits, thereby sparking interest and understanding among primary school students. Additionally, the role of community sensitization meetings, as demonstrated in the Ugandan study, underscores the importance of leveraging social networks to disseminate information and engage a wider audience (Kakuhikire et al., 2021). By organizing such meetings, educators can ensure that information about biomass energy reaches the students, their families, and the broader community, fostering a supportive learning environment. Finally, the medical student outreach project illustrates the need for reflection and adaptation in community engagement initiatives. Ensuring that educational content is appropriately pitched and that there is room for feedback and reflection can enhance the learning experience for students (Brown et al., 2023). In conclusion, effective community engagement and outreach in teaching primary school students about biomass for biodiesel require a collaborative approach that involves community stakeholders, strategic outreach efforts, and continuous reflection and adaptation of educational content. These strategies can help create a more engaging and impactful learning experience for students.

Discussion

While utilizing biomass for biodiesel production in primary education presents numerous benefits, some notable challenges and limitations must be addressed to ensure its effective implementation. One of the main challenges is the availability and accessibility of appropriate biomass feedstock, which can vary depending on geographical location and resource availability. Additionally, there may be concerns regarding the scalability of biomass production to meet the biodiesel needs of a large population, raising questions about the sustainability and long-term viability of such

initiatives (Srivastava et al., 2020). To overcome these challenges, educators should foster partnerships with local industries and universities to access resources and expertise while incorporating sustainability and environmental stewardship lessons to instill a sense of responsibility and awareness in students. By addressing these limitations head-on, primary schools can maximize the potential of biomass for biodiesel education.

Upon reflection of the current state of research on utilizing biomass for biodiesel production in primary education, it is evident that further investigation is warranted to enhance the pedagogical approach and practical applications in teaching this concept. Integrating new findings from the research into educational curricula can foster critical thinking skills and encourage students to explore the complex interactions between environmental science, sustainable practices, and economic considerations within the context of biomass utilization for biodiesel production. Future research in this field should focus on developing comprehensive teaching resources that incorporate real-world examples and promote a holistic understanding of the potential impacts and challenges associated with sustainable energy solutions in primary school settings.

Educators are pivotal in shaping the next generation's understanding of sustainable practices and environmental consciousness. Considering the increasing urgency to address climate change, educators must incorporate lessons about renewable energy sources, such as biomass for biodiesel, into their curriculum. By integrating these concepts into their teaching, educators can instill a sense of responsibility towards the planet and equip students with the knowledge and skills necessary to make informed decisions. To effectively educate students on the benefits of biomass for biodiesel, educators must stay informed about current research and developments in the field. Additionally, they should collaborate with industry experts and invite guest speakers to provide real-world examples. By taking this proactive approach, educators can inspire the next generation to become leaders in sustainability and work towards a more environmentally conscious future (Rosillo-Calle & Woods, 2012)..

Conclusion

Integrating biomass education in primary schools for biodiesel production is a promising approach to promoting sustainability and environmental awareness among young students. By engaging children in hands-on activities such as growing crops for biofuel production, educators can instill a sense of responsibility and stewardship toward the environment from an early age. Additionally, teaching about biomass and biodiesel can help students understand the importance of renewable energy sources and challenge conventional ideas about fossil fuels. While there may be challenges in implementing such programs, the long-term benefits of educating future generations about sustainable practices outweigh any initial obstacles. As more research is conducted on the effectiveness of integrating biomass education in primary education curricula, educators must continue to explore innovative ways to inspire young minds to become environmental advocates and change agents in their communities.

Teaching primary school students about biomass for biodiesel involves emphasizing key points such as the importance of sustainable energy sources, understanding how to convert biomass into biodiesel, and recognizing the environmental benefits of using biodiesel as a fuel alternative. By introducing students to these concepts early, educators can instill a sense of environmental responsibility and awareness that may shape their future attitudes and behaviors toward sustainability. Incorporating hands-

on activities and experiments into the curriculum can help reinforce these key points and deepen student understanding of the topic. Overall, educating young learners about biomass for biodiesel promotes scientific literacy and cultivates a generation of environmentally conscious citizens equipped to address the complex energy challenges of the future. (Love & Bryant, 2017)

Teaching biomass for biodiesel in primary schools is essential for developing a foundation of environmental awareness and sustainability at a young age. Educators can instill a sense of responsibility and stewardship towards the planet by introducing students to renewable resources like biomass for fuel production. This early exposure can spark an interest in alternative energy sources and encourage critical thinking about energy consumption and conservation. Research has shown that early education in sustainability can positively impact attitudes and behaviors towards the environment in the long term. Additionally, teaching about biomass for biodiesel can provide students with valuable knowledge and skills that are increasingly relevant in a world facing climate change and energy crises. As such, integrating this topic into the primary education curriculum can contribute to creating informed and environmentally conscious future generations.

In conclusion, integrating biomass as a practical learning tool for biodiesel production in primary education offers a range of benefits. Educators can foster a deeper understanding of renewable resources and environmental conservation by providing hands-on experiences for students to engage with sustainable practices, such as cultivating energy crops and converting them into biofuels. Students can develop critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and a sense of social responsibility towards the planet through this experiential learning approach. Moreover, incorporating biomass education into the curriculum can help address the growing demand for individuals with knowledge and skills in alternative energy sources. As primary education plays a crucial role in shaping young minds and attitudes, embracing biomass education can empower the next generation to become environmentally conscious citizens and future leaders in sustainability.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Abbasi, T., & Abbasi, S. (2010). Biomass energy and the environmental impacts associated with its production and utilization. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 14(3), 919-937. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2009.11.006>
- Abdullah, S. H. Y. S., Hanapi, N. H. M., Azid, A., Umar, R., Juahir, H., Khatoon, H., & Endut, A. (2017). A review of biomass-derived heterogeneous catalyst for a sustainable biodiesel production. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 70, 1040-1051. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.12.008>
- Agirreazkuenaga, L. (2022). Environmental and sustainability education: A critical analysis of evaluation instruments through a research-practice partnership. *Environmental Education Research*, 28(5), 695-714. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2022.2031898>

- Arief, N. N., Famiola, M., Pratama, A. P., Anggahegari, P., & Putri, A. N. (2021). Sustainability Communication through Bio-Based Experiential Learning. *Sustainability*, 14(9), 5204. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095204>
- Athar, M., & Zaidi, S. (2020). A review of the feedstocks, catalysts, and intensification techniques for sustainable biodiesel production. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 8(6), 104523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.104523>
- Babu, S., Singh Rathore, S., Singh, R., Kumar, S., Singh, V. K., Yadav, S., Yadav, V., Raj, R., Yadav, D., Shekhawat, K., & Ali Wani, O. (2022). Exploring agricultural waste biomass for energy, food and feed production and pollution mitigation: A review. *Bioresource Technology*, 360, 127566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127566>
- Bencresciuto, G. F., Mandalà, C., Migliori, C. A., Giansante, L., Di Giacinto, L., & Bardi, L. (2024). Microbial Biotechnologies to Produce Biodiesel and Biolubricants from Dairy Effluents. *Fermentation*, 10(6), 278. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation10060278>
- Brown, M. E., Ahuja, N., Sivam, V., Khanna, A., & Parekh, R. (2023). A qualitative evaluation of the impact of a medical student school outreach project on both medical students and school pupils. *BMJ open*, 13(11), e070508. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-070508>
- Carpenter, D., Westover, T. L., Czernik, S., & Jablonski, W. (2014). Biomass feedstocks for renewable fuel production: a review of the impacts of feedstock and pretreatment on the yield and product distribution of fast pyrolysis bio-oils and vapors. *Green Chemistry*, 16(2), 384-406. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3GC41631C>
- Cheng, J. (2017). *Biomass to renewable energy processes* (2nd ed.). CRC Press.
- Chozhavendhan, S., Vijay Pradhap Singh, M., Fransila, B., Praveen Kumar, R., & Karthiga Devi, G. (2020). A review on influencing parameters of biodiesel production and purification processes. *Current Research in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*, 1-2, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crgsc.2020.04.002>
- Clase, K., Adedokun, O., & Ha, S. (2014). Introducing teachers to emerging interdisciplinary STEM content through biomass and biofuels research (618.36). *The FASEB Journal*, 28, 618.36. https://doi.org/10.1096/fasebj.28.1_supplement.618.36
- Dahiya, A. (Ed.). (2014). *Bioenergy: Biomass to Biofuels*. Academic Pres.
- Demirbas, A., & Fatih-Demirbas, M. (2010). Importance of algae oil as a source of biodiesel. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 52(1), 163-170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2010.06.055>
- EduGorilla Prep Experts. (2022). *HTET Level-I Exam 2022: Haryana Primary Teacher (PRT) | 8 Full-length Mock Tests + 3 Previous Year Papers (1600+ Solved Questions)*. EduGorilla Community Pvt. Ltd.
- Eldiehy, K. S., Bardhan, P., Borah, D., Gohain, M., Rather, M. A., Deka, D., & Mandal, M. (2022). A comprehensive review on microalgal biomass production and processing for biodiesel production. *Fuel*, 324, 124773. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2022.124773>
- Erku, D., Khatri, R., Endalamaw, A., Wolka, E., Nigatu, F., Zewdie, A., & Assefa, Y. (2023). Community engagement initiatives in primary health care to achieve universal health coverage: A realist synthesis of scoping review. *PLOS ONE*, 18(5), e0285222. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0285222>

- Goel, A., Jain, S., Addya, A., Srivastava, S., Pandey, R., & Rathi, S. (2022). Student Perceptions of Environmental Education in India. *Sustainability*, 15(21), 15346. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152115346>
- Güney, T., & Kantar, K. (2020). Biomass energy consumption and sustainable development. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 27(8), 762–767. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504509.2020.1753124>
- Hajjari, M., Tabatabaei, M., Aghbashlo, M., & Ghanavati, H. (2017). A review on the prospects of sustainable biodiesel production: A global scenario with an emphasis on waste-oil biodiesel utilization. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 72, 445-464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.034>
- Hamza, M., Ayoub, M., Shamsuddin, R. B., Mukhtar, A., Saqib, S., Zahid, I., Ameen, M., Ullah, S., Al-Sehemi, A. G., & Ibrahim, M. (2021). A review on the waste biomass derived catalysts for biodiesel production. *Environmental Technology & Innovation*, 21, 101200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2020.101200>
- Han, G., & Martin, R. A. (2018). Teaching and Learning about Biomass Energy: The Significance of Biomass Education in Schools. *Sustainability*, 10(4), 996. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10040996>
- Hernández-Barco, M. A., Sánchez-Martín, J., Corbacho-Cuello, I., & Cañada-Cañada, F. (2022). Is sustainability an exhausted concept? Bridging the gap from environmental awareness to emotional proficiency in science education through integral sustainability. *Heliyon*, 8(12), e12546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e12546>
- Holstermann, N., Grube, D., & Bögeholz, S. (2010). Hands-on activities and their influence on students' interest. *Research in Science Education*, 40(5), 743-757. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-009-9142-0>
- Kakuhikire, B., Satinsky, E. N., Baguma, C., Rasmussen, J. D., Perkins, J. M., Gumisiriza, P., ... & Tsai, A. C. (2021). Correlates of attendance at community engagement meetings held in advance of bio-behavioral research studies: A longitudinal, sociocentric social network study in rural Uganda. *PLoS medicine*, 18(7), e1003705. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1003705>
- Kong, S., & Wang, Y. (2023). Monitoring cognitive development through the assessment of computational thinking practices: A longitudinal intervention on primary school students. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 145, 107749. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.107749>
- Kumar, P. M. (2016). Curriculum Enrichment for Learning Outcomes in Higher Education. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education ISSN (Online): 2455 – 5630, Volume I, Issue II, 175-183*, Available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3061507>
- Kvestad, I., Chandyo, R. K., Schwinger, C., Ranjitkar, S., Hysing, M., Ulak, M., Shrestha, M., Shrestha, L., & Strand, T. A. (2022). Biomass fuel use for cooking in Nepalese families and child cognitive abilities, results from a community-based study. *Environmental Research*, 212, 113265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.113265>
- Lin, W., Padmanabhan, G., Pryor, S., & Wiesenborn, D. (2007, June). Introducing Native American Community College Students To Engineering Through Hands On Exploratory Projects. In *2007 Annual Conference & Exposition* (pp. 12-974). <https://doi.org/10.18260/1-2--2563>

- Love, J., & Bryant, J. A. (2017). *Biofuels and Bioenergy*. John Wiley & Sons.
- McCormack, L., Finlayson, O. E., & McCloughlin, T. J. J. (2014). The CASE Programme Implemented Across the Primary and Secondary School Transition in Ireland. *International Journal of Science Education*, 36(17), 2892–2917. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2014.938711>
- Mitra, M., Nagchaudhuri, A., Henry, X. S. D., & Shirvani, C. R. (2015). Bioenergy Academy for Teachers (BEAT) Promotes Multidisciplinary Content in STEM Education. In *2015 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition* (pp. 26-282). <https://doi.org/10.18260/p.23621>
- Moirano, R., Sánchez, M. A., & Štěpánek, L. (2020). Creative interdisciplinary collaboration: A systematic literature review. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 35, 100626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2019.100626>
- Molino, A., Larocca, V., Chianese, S., & Musmarra, D. (2018). Biofuels Production by Biomass Gasification: A Review. *Energies*, 11(4), 811. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11040811>
- Nicholls, D. L. (2008). *A synthesis of biomass utilization for bioenergy production in the Western United States*. U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Pacific Northwest Research Station.
- Ogunkunle, O., & Ahmed, N. A. (2019). A review of global current scenario of biodiesel adoption and combustion in vehicular diesel engines. *Energy Reports*, 5, 1560-1579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2019.10.028>
- Oktaweri, S., Festiyed, & Djamas, D. (2019). Curriculum analysis in developing interactive multimedia teaching materials scientific model assisted games for physics learning. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1185(1), 012118. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1185/1/012118>
- Osman, A. I., Chen, L., Yang, M., Msigwa, G., Farghali, M., Fawzy, S., & Yap, P.-S. (2022). Cost, environmental impact, and resilience of renewable energy under a changing climate: A review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 21(4), 2385-2485. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-022-01532-8>
- Peters, M., Stokes, J., & Tu, R. (2019). Conversion of Omega-3 Fatty Acids from Algae Biomass Produced Biodiesel. *Univ. of Pennsylvania Library—https://repository.upenn.edu/cbe_sdr*. Available at: https://repository.upenn.edu/cbe_sdr/116
- Riesch, S. K., Ngui, E. M., Ehlert, C., Miller, M. K., Cronk, C. A., Leuthner, S., Strehlow, M., Hewitt, J. B., & Durkin, M. S. (2013). Community Outreach and Engagement Strategies from the Wisconsin Study Center of the National Children's Study. *Public Health Nursing*, 30(3), 254-265. <https://doi.org/10.1111/phn.12018>
- Rosillo-Calle, F., & Woods, J. (2012). *The biomass assessment handbook* (Vol. 4). Taylor & Francis.
- Rosillo-Calle, F., de Groot, P., Hemstock, S. L., & Woods, J. (2015). *The Biomass Assessment Handbook: Energy for a Sustainable Environment* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Science Teachers Association of Nigeria. (2007). *Strategies for environmental education: Focus on mineral and energy resources*. Science Teachers Association of Nigeria.
- Scragg, A. H. (2009). *Biofuels: Production, Application and Development*. CABI.

- Singh, D., Sharma, D., Soni, S., Inda, C. S., Sharma, S., Sharma, P. K., & Jhalani, A. (2021). A comprehensive review of biodiesel production from waste cooking oil and its use as fuel in compression ignition engines: 3rd generation cleaner feedstock. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 307, 127299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127299>
- Speight, J. G., & Singh, K. (2014). *Environmental management of energy from biofuels and biofeedstocks*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Sri Shalini, S., Palanivelu, K., Ramachandran, A., & Raghavan, V. (2021). Biochar from biomass waste as a renewable carbon material for climate change mitigation in reducing greenhouse gas emissions—a review. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, 11(5), 2247-2267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-020-00604-5>
- Srivastava, N., Srivastava, M., Mishra, P. K., & Gupta, V. K. (2020). *Biofuel Production Technologies: Critical Analysis for Sustainability*. Springer Nature.
- Thornley, P., Gilbert, P., Shackley, S., & Hammond, J. (2015). Maximizing the greenhouse gas reductions from biomass: The role of life cycle assessment. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 81, 35-43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2015.05.002>
- United States. Congress. Senate. Committee on Appropriations. Subcommittee on Energy and Water, and Related Agencies. (2005). *Energy and water, and related agencies appropriations for fiscal year 2006: Hearing before a subcommittee of the Committee on Appropriations, United States Senate, One Hundred Ninth Congress, first session, on H.R. 2419, an act making appropriations for energy and water development for the fiscal year ending September 30, 2006, and for other purposes*. U.S. Government Printing Office.
- Vesterinen, M., & Ratinen, I. (2023). Sustainability competences in primary school education – a systematic literature review. *Environmental Education Research*, 30(1), 56–67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2023.2170984>
- Wang, H., Peng, X., Zhang, H., Yang, S., & Li, H. (2021). Microorganisms-promoted biodiesel production from biomass: A review. *Energy Conversion and Management: X*, 12, 100137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2021.100137>